

Effect of Om Meditation on Mental Health of UGC-NET Aspirants

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Abstract

This research paper investigates the effect of Om meditation on the mental health of UGC NET aspirants. The study recognizes the challenges faced by students during exam preparation and the potential impact on their mental well-being. Om meditation, a traditional practice in Hinduism, Buddhism, and Jainism, is explored for its positive effects on mental health, including stress reduction, improved concentration, emotional regulation, and enhanced self-awareness. The research employs the Mental Health Inventory (M.H.I) by Dr. Jagdish and Dr. A. K. Srivastava to assess various dimensions of mental health before and after Om meditation practice. Statistical analysis reveals significant improvements across dimensions such as Positive Self Evaluation, Perception of Reality, Personality Integration, Autonomy, Goal Oriented Attitudes, Environmental Mastery, and Total Mental Health. The findings suggest that consistent practice of Om meditation can enhance the overall mental health of UGC NET aspirants, providing a valuable tool for managing stress and promoting well-being during the demanding exam preparation phase.

Keywords: Om Meditation, Mental Health, UGC NET Aspirants, Stress Reduction.

Introduction

College-going youth undergo an important phase where they face ups and downs. High points and low points occur frequently. Many students are preparing for the competitive exams. Preparing for the exam requires extensive dedication and hard work, which can take a toll on the mental health of the aspirants. Struggling learners unable to cope risk wellness problems: physical illness, mental strain (Dol, 2019). Challenges left unchecked can harm health. Without sound mental health students' life becomes difficult to excel in their respective fields.

People are healthy mentally when they feel well and use their abilities effectively. They adequately handle life's pressures and positively contribute to their community. Practicing meditation has good effects physically and mentally. The sound "Om" has a universal, positive force that raises uplifting vibrations and provides a spiritual sensation. (Surlya and Jain, 2021).

With the practice of Om mantra chanting one can achieve a state of mental peace. Om chanting is old. It's strongly used for spiritual reasons in Hinduism, Buddhism, and Jainism. The Om mantra has amazing benefits that can heal stress in minds of people living busy, modern lives. After reciting Om, students feel happier. They have better focus and concentration. Meditation helps develop a balanced, peaceful mind. It promotes and develops mental health of students too. It can be used to treat a variety of mental diseases, tensions, and other emotions (Das and Sarkar, 2023). After reciting Om meditation students feel happier and have improved mental focus and concentration. One of the benefits of meditation is that it can be adapted to the specific needs of individuals with different mental health conditions.

Review of Literature

Study of Baghel (2023) found that Om meditation practice had been shown to improve emotion regulation and cognitive processes, such as attention and memory, which might contribute to the improvements in mental health.

Nayak's study in 2016 found that chanting Om significantly impacts mental health positively. Immersing oneself fully into the mental aspects of Om chanting, not just the physical act, helps enhance overall well-being. Om chanting has profound benefits for improving mental health.

Anand (2014) examined the effect of meditation on mental health and psychological well being. Findings revealed that meditation practice significantly effect the mental health and psychological well being.

Research Methodology

Sampling

Participants in this study were selected from the Amroha district through a purposive random sampling. Total number of students was 20.

Tool Description

The Mental Health Inventory (M.H.I) created by Dr. Jagdish and Dr. A. K. Srivastava has 56 items. They're split into 6 areas: Positive Self Evaluation (10 items), Perception of Reality (8 items), Integration of Personality (12 items), Autonomy (6 items), Group oriented Attitudes (10 items), and Environmental Mastery (10 items). Participants respond on a four-point scale. For positive statements, "Always" scores 4, "Often" scores 3, "Rarely" scores 2, and "Never" scores 1. The scoring is reversed for negative statements. The overall inventory's reliability is 0.73, and the dimensions range from 0.71 to 0.75, calculated via split-half reliability. It has construct validity.

Procedure

People gave data by filling questionnaires. The questionnaire was Mental Health Inventory (M.H.I) by Dr. Jagdish and Dr. A. K. Srivastava. Each student got the questionnaire and answered it. After collecting responses, they scored them using the manual's guide. The scores were analyzed statistically by finding mean, standard deviation, and t-test value.

Table 1
Comparing Pre and Post Test Scores of Om Meditation on
Dimensions of Mental Health for UGC NET Aspirants

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	Mean Difference	t'	p value
Positive Self Evaluation	Pre	23.37	30	3.068	0.560	6.200	28.630	0.000
	Post	29.57	30	3.224	0.589			
Perception of Reality	Pre	19.90	30	3.188	0.582	6.033	30.095	0.000
	Post	25.93	30	3.362	0.614			
Personality Integration	Pre	27.97	30	3.222	0.588	7.167	22.261	0.000
	Post	35.13	30	3.115	0.569			
Autonomy	Pre	15.10	30	3.294	0.601	5.333	23.028	0.000
	Post	20.43	30	3.626	0.662			
Goal Oriented Attitudes	Pre	22.57	30	2.967	0.542	8.133	22.135	0.000
	Post	30.70	30	2.818	0.515			
Environmental Mastery	Pre	20.27	30	3.562	0.650	8.000	68.118	0.000
	Post	28.27	30	3.581	0.654			
Total Mental Health	Pre	129.17	30	9.910	1.809	40.867	56.112	0.000
	Post	170.03	30	10.915	1.993			

The above table indicates that the mean scores for Pre-testing for Positive Self-evaluation dimension of Mental Health is found to be 23.37 and for post testing it was 29.57. The mean difference is 6.200 and the 't' value is found to be 28.360 which is significant at 0.01 level ($p=0.000$; $p < 0.01$). It

infers that there is significant difference in mean scores during pre-testing and post testing for Positive Self-evaluation dimension of Mental Health. Furthermore, the mean score suggest that the mean scores for Positive Self-evaluation dimension of Mental Health are significantly higher at the time of post testing in comparison to pre-testing. It can be inferred that Om Meditation improves Positive Self-evaluation dimension of Mental Health of UGC NET Aspirants.

The above table indicates that the mean scores for Pre-testing for Perception of reality dimension of Mental Health is found to be 19.90 and for post testing it was 25.93. The mean difference is 6.033 and the 't' value is found to be 30.095 which is significant at 0.01 level ($p=0.000$; $p < 0.01$). It infers that there is significant difference in mean scores during pre-testing and post testing for Perception of reality dimension of Mental Health. Furthermore, the mean score suggest that the mean scores for Perception of reality dimension of Mental Health are significantly higher at the time of post testing in comparison to pre-testing. It can be inferred that Om Meditation improves Perception of reality dimension of Mental Health of UGC NET Aspirants.

The above table indicates that the mean scores for Pre-testing for Personality Integration dimension of Happiness is found to be 27.97 and for post testing it was 35.13. The mean difference is 7.167 and the 't' value is found to be 22.261 which is significant at 0.01 level ($p=0.000$; $p < 0.01$). It infers that there is significant difference in mean scores during pre-testing and post testing for Personality Integration dimension of Mental Health. Furthermore, the mean score suggest that the mean scores for Personality Integration dimension of Mental Health are significantly higher at the time of post testing in comparison to pre-testing. It can be inferred that Om Meditation improves Personality Integration dimension of Mental Health of UGC NET Aspirants..

The above table indicates that the mean scores for Pre-testing for Autonomy dimension of Mental Health is found to be 15.10 and for post testing it was 20.43. The mean difference is 5.333 and the 't' value is found to be 23.028 which is significant at 0.01 level ($p=0.000$; $p < 0.01$). It infers that there is significant difference in mean scores during pre-testing and post testing for Autonomy dimension of Mental Health. Furthermore, the mean score suggest that the mean scores for Autonomy dimension of Mental Health are significantly higher at the time of post testing in comparison to pre-testing. It can be inferred that Om Meditation improves Autonomy dimension of Mental Health of UGC NET Aspirants..

The above table indicates that the mean scores for Pre-testing for Goal Oriented Attitudes dimension of Mental Health is found to be 22.57 and for post testing it was 30.70. The mean difference is 8.133 and the 't' value is found to be 22.135 which is significant at 0.01 level ($p=0.000$; $p < 0.01$). It infers that there is significant difference in mean scores during pre-testing and post testing for Goal Oriented Attitudes dimension of Mental Health. Furthermore, the mean score suggest that the mean scores for Goal Oriented Attitudes dimension of Mental Health are significantly higher at the time of post testing in comparison to pre-testing. It can be inferred that Om Meditation improves Goal Oriented Attitudes dimension of Mental Health of UGC NET Aspirants.

The above table indicates that the mean scores for Pre-testing for Environmental Mastery dimension of Mental Health is found to be 20.27 and for post testing it was 28.27. The mean difference is 8.000 and the 't' value is found to be 68.118 which is significant at 0.01 level ($p=0.000$; $p < 0.01$). It infers that there is significant difference in mean scores during pre-testing and post testing for Environmental Mastery dimension of Mental Health. Furthermore, the mean score suggest that the mean scores for Environmental Mastery dimension of Mental Health are significantly higher at the time of post testing in comparison to pre-testing. It can be inferred that Om Meditation improves Environmental Mastery dimension of Mental Health of UGC NET Aspirants.

The above table indicates that the mean scores for Pre-testing for Total dimensions of Mental Health is found to be 129.17 and for post testing it was 170.03. The mean difference is 40.867 and the 't' value is found to be 56.112 which is significant at 0.01 level ($p=0.000$; $p < 0.01$). It infers that there is significant difference in mean scores during pre-testing and post testing for total dimensions of Mental Health. Furthermore, the mean score suggest that the mean scores for total dimensions of Mental Health are significantly higher at the time of post testing in comparison to pre-testing. It can be inferred that Om Meditation improves total dimensions of Mental Health of UGC NET Aspirants.

Conclusion

"Om" meditation, often referred to as "Aum" meditation, is a form of mantra meditation that involves chanting the sound "Om" or "Aum" repeatedly. The effect of Om meditation may include:

- **Stress Reduction:** Om meditation involves rhythmic and focused chanting, which can help induce a state of relaxation. Regular practice of Om meditation may reduce stress and anxiety levels, which are common among students preparing for competitive exams.
- **Improved Concentration and Focus:** Chanting the "Om" sound repetitively can help train the mind to stay focused on a single point. Aspirants can experience enhanced concentration, allowing them to study more effectively and with greater attention to detail.
- **Enhanced Clarity of Thought:** Om meditation may help clear the mind of clutter and unnecessary thoughts, allowing aspirants to think more clearly and make decisions with greater clarity.
- **Emotional Regulation:** Engaging in Om meditation might help aspirants regulate their emotions, enabling them to manage feelings of frustration, anxiety, and self-doubt often associated with exam preparation.
- **Reduced Negative Self-Talk:** The repetitive chanting of "Om" can replace negative self-talk with a calming and positive focus. This shift could contribute to a more constructive inner dialogue, promoting self-confidence and a healthier self-concept.
- **Mindfulness and Present-Moment Awareness:** The act of chanting requires present-moment awareness. This practice can cultivate mindfulness, helping aspirants stay in the present rather than getting overwhelmed by future concerns.
- **Strengthened Resilience:** Regular meditation practice, including Om meditation, can contribute to increased resilience. Aspirants may develop the ability to bounce back from setbacks and maintain a positive attitude despite challenges.
- **Better Sleep Quality:** Om Meditation relaxation effects could positively impact sleep quality, ensuring that aspirants get sufficient rest during the demanding period of exam preparation.
- **Self-Care and Relaxation:** Engaging in Om meditation provides aspirants with an opportunity for self-care and relaxation, which is crucial for maintaining overall mental well-being during the rigorous preparation phase.
- **Increased Self-Awareness:** Om meditation encourages self-awareness as individuals tune in to the vibrations and sensations associated with chanting. This heightened self-awareness can lead to better understanding and management of one's mental and emotional state.

In a nutshell it can be said that consistency and patience are key when it comes to experiencing the benefits of meditation. Aspirants interested in incorporating Om meditation into their routine should seek guidance from a qualified meditation instructor and consider complementing their practice with other healthy study habits and stress management techniques.

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